

EASY WAYS OF LEARNING AND TEACHING ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Ne'matullayeva Nodirabegim Nodirovna

Student of Uzbek State World Languages University

Scientific advisor: Khodjayeva Saodatkhan Saidullayevna

Abstract. One of the pressing problems today is how to learn English quickly and easily. Along with this, language learning is becoming the need of the hour. In this article, I want to show you easy and convenient ways to learn and teach English. If I start with language teaching, the main aspect that we need to pay attention to is the age of the language learner.

Keywords: instructions, politest language, listen first, teach English, pay attention, language learner, playing Scrabble, avoid (keep away from) metalanguage, drill, repeat, second Language.

Introduction.

Today, the ability to know foreign languages is becoming an integral part of our lives. Due to the high rate of cooperation with foreign partners among specialists of various fields, their demand for languages is high. In modern society, foreign languages are becoming an important part of professional training. People learn this knowledge first in preschool institutions, then at school in institutes, training courses or independently. Success in achieving this goal depends on the practical methods and teacher skills. The ability to use information technologies and teaching methods helps to quickly understand new materials. By combining different methods, the teacher will be able to solve specific educational programs.

In teaching English, it is best to teach by depending on the potential, level and age of the learner. How to learn English quickly and easily? We know that learning a language is not an easy task. It requires patience and hard work from us. In the following article, we will talk about effective ways to learn English easily and quickly. And so, the following methods and easy tips of teaching can be used to teach English in a meaningful and interesting way:

1. Keep instructions clear, understandable and simple

It can be tempting when addressing a class of students, especially ones that you've only just met, to explain activities and functions in your politest language. After all, nobody likes to be rude. However, a student who has only a few words of English language, if any at all, won't appreciate the courtesy of (or even understand or catch on), "OK, so now what I'd like you all to do, if you don't mind, is just to stand up for a moment and come to the front of the class. Oh, and please bring your book and notebook with you. Could we all just do that kind of thing?"

Instead of it, make instructions crystal clear by using as few words as necessary, important and by gesturing whenever possible, and break down series of instructions into smaller units. If you want to be so polite, "please" and "thank you" will do. "Everyone – take your book, please. Stand up. Now, come here, sit down, please. Thanks."

2. Let them (learners) listen first

More than likely, your students will want to begin practising speaking pretty much from the get-go. However, it takes a while for one's ear to acclimatise to the sounds of a new kind of language, and not everybody will be so keen; don't put pressure students into speaking before they've had lots of opportunity to listen to you using it (which doesn't mean you should just be rambling on at the front of the classroom – with beginners more so than with other levels, you really have to consider what you say and grade your new language accordingly).

3. *Drill, repeat, drill, repeat, drill, repeat ...*

Beginners need plenty of repetition and drilling, especially as they get to grips with the sounds of their new language. It may seem boring to go over the same sentences again and again, but it is necessary and important. When practising a new sentence, try, again and again, back-drilling, breaking the sentence down into manageable units and then building it back up, working backwards from the end of the sentence to the beginning; this helps to ensure that your intonation is natural and that you get elements of connected speech right and your speech might be sounded like a native one's. For instance, break down "Would you like a cup of coffee?" as follows:

coffee > cup of coffee > like a > like a cup of coffee > Would you > Would you like a cup of coffee?

4. *Establish class language early on*

Class (classroom) language – Can you speak more slowly? What must we do? I don't get it. What does this mean? How do you say this kind of word in English? – is usually associated with teaching children, but it really helps with adults as well. No matter how friendly or relaxed you make your classroom atmosphere, learning a new kind of language can still be daunting, especially when you feel you're not completely following what's going on, or that you may be called on to say something that you don't feel ready to say. It's much better to equip students early on with classroom language that will lend a hand them navigate the lesson smoothly.

5. *Avoid (keep away from) metalanguage*

There's no point in students knowing the terms past simple tense, irregular verb or adverb of frequency if they can't use the actual structures or words they refer to. Don't tell them how to say something: let them know. Give as much context as you can (visual and clear prompts work well). What's more, make sure you check they have understood by asking questions that test their comprehension – never ask "Do you realize?" as a) many people are reluctant to let on that they haven't comprehended and will pretend instead that they have; and b) a student might think they have understood when in fact they haven't.

6. *Don't forget that your students are fluent in their own (native) language(s)*

This might seem a trivial point, but it's all too easy and clear when listening to someone speaking broken English to forget that behind the faults and the mispronunciation is a person with cogent opinions, no doubt accurate in their first language, attempting to communicate his or her thoughts or ideas. As teachers, we not only have to be patient and proactive, motivated listeners, alert to the reasons, why certain faults are being made while filling in the sentences in less-than-perfect communication, we also must steer clear of adopting the Me-Tarzan-You-Jane approach to teaching, bastardizing the very language we are approaching to teach. Rather than degrading our source language we need to grade it carefully so as to preserve it comprehensible while maintaining its naturalness, rhythm and spirit, ensuring all the while that, as far as possible, we actually converse with our students and listen to what they need to say. After that, even from the first lessons, from the 'A' in the alphabet and the 'am' of 'to be', communication is the goal, purpose.

In addition, bear in mind that, unlike with higher levels, you can't rely on conversations developing simply since the students don't yet have the linguistic resources to engage in anything other than simple exchanges (though in time they will). This means that the onus will largely be on you to keep them speaking. Finally, enjoy the level. Although in many ways the hardest and the most difficult level to teach, this can also be one of the most satisfying. Seeing your learners don't go from knowing anything to knowing a few words to knowing a few sentences and

structures to being able to hold rudimentary conversations can be incredibly rewarding, and if they enjoy their initial exposure to the new language, and feel confident and inspired to go on, then you will have helped pave the way to their further success, career.

When you are learning English, it's essential to keep your motivation up. As with any task, there might be times when it feels a bit more difficult than ever, so switch up your methods and don't be afraid to make faults and mistakes – you'll, of course, reach the level you want to be at. We've already provided some unique ways to teach an English language that you might now have experienced with your teacher. Here, we suggest some easy ways to learn English that you can try any time – at home, at college, on the way, at work or on the move. Why not try them today or now? Surround yourself with English atmosphere and you'll see improvements and achievements in your language confidence and skills, while having fun at the same time.

1. English words with friends, classmates

Scrabble is a classic board game in which players use random lettered tiles to create new words in a crossword fashion. It's a fantastic also interesting way to strengthen your English vocabulary, and there's also a Scrabble Junior version for beginner students. Playing Scrabble challenges, you to really think in English as you try to come up with different difficult words using your set of letters.

If you are taking an English lesson, buy the board game and invite your friends to play with you. You may also play Scrabble online through websites like Facebook, where it is called Words with Friends.

2. Unify some music

Not only will your lovely song wake up your mind and put you in a positive mood to learn English, but the lyrics can lend a hand you expand your skills. Research illustrates how music can help second language learners acquire grammar and vocabulary and improve spelling.

Songs almost always contain a lot of useful vocabulary, phrasal verbs, phrases and expressions. And since the intended audience is native speakers, the latest tunes include up-to-date language sources and colloquialisms. The language words used in songs is casual and usable, if you pick the right music. Music also has an uncanny ability to stick in our heads, so this can support you to remember your new English words vocabulary.

3. Try, try and try again until you learn

To commit new English words and vocabulary to memory, it's necessary to keep using them. Keep a notebook of new English words you learn, and try to use them in three different complex and simple sentences. Write your gaps down and say them out loud. The repetition will help you to remember the new word, and working out different difficult uses of the word will help expand your bank of vocabulary. Remember, taking small steps like these will still support you to reach your goal.

4. Join online English forums, which are very helpful

The key here is to join online forums for subjects that you are interested in – that way, your motivation will rub off on your English learning words and you'll be more inclined to participate in. So, whether it's photography, movies, films, travelling or cooking, discuss your passion with other like-minded people in English.

If you feel nervous about people identifying yourself, make an anonymous profile. Then read through the online forum to see what people are discussing. Once you feel confident, start to actively take part in the online forum by responding questions posed by other people – or post your special questions and have a conversation with the other members who answer you.

5. *Get with the English language*

One of the most effective, efficient and easy ways to learn English is to fully immerse yourself in the language. Find an English-speaking radio station to listen to, watch an English-speaking movie, film or TV show or surround yourself with people having conversations in English language. Listen carefully to conversations in restaurants, cafes, on the bus or in shops and try to pick up the everyday use of the English language. Not only will this support your listening skills, but you can also try to pronounce the words yourself in context to develop your speaking skills. With up-to-date technology and apps, this can be done practically anywhere.

6. *Read to learn English language*

You could really give your reading comprehension skills a boost here – but your speaking skills may benefit, too. The more you read English text to yourself or aloud, the more confidence you will have for yourself. If you feel nervous, start by practising at home then move on to reading in front of an audience and asking for their feedback, faults. Of course, it's also enjoyable to read some wonderful, amazing stories.

In fact, learning languages through the senses is useful and efficient than other methods. For example, tasting a single apple, the student knows its color, taste, size, smell, also pronounces its English name. As a result, when the teacher asks the learners the names of the colors, the learners immediately remember when they ate the fruit. Therefore, the use of such methods helps the student to long information in his memory.

In conclusion, teaching language to language learners not as a duty, but on the contrary, using interesting games and innovative methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. Therefore, as the educational system also sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we can make our contribution by developing the ways of effective use of innovative technologies.

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